

“Still Hysterical?": Endometriosis and the Gendered Failure of Medicine

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Giovanni Spitale¹ 0000-0002-6812-0979

Federico Germani¹ 0000-0002-5604-0437

Angela Bonato² 0000-0001-5991-2483

Nikola Biller-Andorno³ 0000-0001-7661-1324

Maide Barış^{4,*} 0000-0001-7445-4599

1: ITE Lab, Institute of Biomedical Ethics and History of Medicine, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

2: Independent researcher; patient

3: Institute of Biomedical Ethics and History of Medicine, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

4: Department of Medical History & Ethics, Marmara University, School of Medicine, Istanbul, Türkiye

*: Corresponding Author; maide.baris@marmara.edu.tr

Abstract

In this paper we examine the persistent diagnostic delays in endometriosis as emblematic of a broader, gendered failure within contemporary medicine. Despite affecting approximately one in ten women of reproductive age, endometriosis remains underdiagnosed, with an average delay up to ten years. This paper situates such delays not solely in clinical complexity, but within a historical and epistemic lineage of medical disbelief toward women's pain. From the ancient concept of the "wandering womb" to modern dismissals of menstrual suffering, we trace how structural biases and androcentric models of care continue to shape diagnostic practices. Drawing on historical analysis and current health policy data, we argue that diagnostic encounters are not merely technical acts, but ethical moments in which credibility, recognition, and justice are at stake. We propose a reframing of diagnostic responsibility through the lens of epistemic justice, reproductive autonomy, and gender-sensitive care.

Endometriosis, we contend, offers a critical example for rethinking how medicine listens, sees, and responds to gendered experiences of pain.

Keywords

Endometriosis; Epistemic injustice; Gender bias; Diagnostic delay; Medical ethics

Statements and declarations

Competing interests

None to declare

Acknowledgements

This paper is dedicated to Silvia, and to all women who experience endometriosis monthly, in pain.

Introduction

The history of hysteria is not merely a remnant of a superstitious past. For much of modern medical history, women reporting pelvic or menstrual pain, including what we now recognize as endometriosis, were frequently dismissed, misdiagnosed or pathologized as "hysterical." This legacy may still echo in the present, reflected in the state of sexual medicine today. Nowhere is this more visible than in the case of endometriosis: a condition that affects roughly one in ten women of reproductive age (Parasar et al. 2017; WHO 2025), yet often remains undiagnosed for an average of seven to ten years despite clear symptoms (Ballard et al. 2006; De Corte et al. 2025). If such a widespread and debilitating disease can evade recognition for up to a decade, then it exposes how medicine still struggles to comprehend and address the deep-seated complexities of female sexual health.

From the ancient myth of the "wandering womb" - the Greek belief that the uterus could physically move through the body causing suffocation, pain, or emotional disturbance (Tasca et al. 2012; King 2016) – to the tendency to minimize women's (monthly or less regular) pain during modern clinical encounters, a familiar pattern of systematic disbelief, underestimation, and quiet marginalization of women's experiences with their sexual health seems to persist (Jones 2015; Cornish 2019; Jackson 2021; Hossain 2021).

Endometriosis was first diagnosed nearly a century ago (Lippi et al. 2022), but that does not mean it did not exist earlier. For some, its late recognition reflects the diagnostic challenges it presents, for endometriosis has distinct histological characteristics yet lacks easily distinguishable pathognomonic clinical features that make diagnosis straightforward (Lippi et al. 2022). However, this explanation alone may be insufficient. Many other conditions share a similar gap between experience and diagnosis: several diseases that were "felt" long before they were formally named, yet they were still acknowledged as legitimate medical entities. For instance, *tuberculosis* was clinically described and socially recognized centuries before Koch's identification of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in 1882 or histological confirmation (Daniel 2006). Often called 'consumption', TB was symptomatically recognized as a major disease during the 18th and 19th centuries, especially among urban working men and poorer classes; historical statistics show that in England in 1838-39 up to a third of tradesmen and employees died of TB, compared with about one-sixth of the upper class (Barberis et al. 2017). Although the exact causes were not known until Robert Koch's identification of the bacillus, such social recognition preceded histological diagnosis. Additionally, modern gender epidemiology underlines the longstanding male predominance in TB incidence;

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a pattern which may reflect structural exposure and social roles rather than purely biological difference (Marçôa et al. 2018).

The historical delay in recognizing endometriosis, therefore, cannot be attributed solely to the limits of medical technology or knowledge. Rather it reveals a deeper and more persistent issue: the systematic underestimation of women's pain and the tendency to question the legitimacy of their bodily experiences (Chen et al. 2008; Hoffmann and Tarzian 2001; Samulowitz et al. 2018; Guzikevits et al. 2024).

This paper therefore bridges two complementary domains. Sexual medicine seeks to understand the biological and reproductive mechanisms underlying conditions (Jannini 2023). Gender medicine, by contrast, interrogates how social norms, institutional structures, and implicit biases shape the recognition and treatment of those conditions (Baggio et al. 2013). While gender medicine is sometimes narrowly interpreted as sex-based stratification in clinical trials or differential drug response – an approach that risks reducing complex gendered experiences to biological variation alone – it also encompasses the broader social, epistemic, and structural dimensions of health that remain under-addressed in many contemporary settings. In other contexts, gender medicine is aligned with LGBTQIA+ health concerns, which are important but distinct from the specific epistemic issue addressed here. The argument that follows draws on this wider understanding of gender medicine: it treats endometriosis not only as a clinical disorder of the reproductive system, but as a case study in the epistemic and ethical failures that arise when gendered experiences of pain are mistrusted or ignored.

From wandering wombs to invisible pain

For much of history, pain itself was considered an intrinsic feature of the female condition, a naturalized and seemingly inevitable aspect of womanhood (Jackson 2021; Hossain 2021). This assumption is visible across a wide range of practices and institutions: from the persistence of female genital mutilation in many societies, to the often abysmal quality of abortion care where pain relief is still inconsistently offered, to the remarkably slow acceptance and development of adequate analgesia during childbirth. Such examples illustrate how women's pain has long been treated as expected, tolerable, or even irrelevant, setting the stage for contemporary patterns in which women's reports of suffering are discounted or normalized rather than investigated (Samulowitz et al. 2018; Jones 2015). Since antiquity, women's suffering has often been interpreted using metaphors that sought to explain rather than genuinely investigate. The ancient Greek conceptualization of *hystera*, in which the uterus was imagined as a restless, mischievous organ with a mind of its

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own, provided an early framework for explaining convulsions, fainting, and other “nervous” ailments in women (Tasca et al. 2012; King 2016). By the nineteenth century, “hysteria” had evolved into a broad diagnostic category encompassing a wide range of symptoms that medicine could not yet explain (Showalter 1997).

Although medical language has changed, certain epistemic patterns appear to persist. Even today, research shows that women reporting chronic pain may have their symptoms dismissed as psychological or imaginary (Samulowitz et al. 2018). This dynamic does not exist in a vacuum: when women’s pain is normalized or minimized, it also reinforces broader social arrangements in which women are expected to function within the domestic sphere rather than as full competitors in the workplace. In contexts where women’s public and economic participation has historically been constrained, the routine dismissal of their pain conveniently aligns with societal expectations that they “cope” rather than seek recognition or accommodation. Conditions such as endometriosis continue to demonstrate how women’s pain can still be misinterpreted and misunderstood, normalized, or rendered invisible within medical discourse (Jones 2015; Cornish 2019). Although hysteria may have disappeared from diagnostic manuals, replaced by terms such as somatization, the deeper epistemic pattern of discrediting women’s reports of pain continues to manifest in subtle yet consequential ways. This dynamic is reinforced by a biomedical culture that still prioritizes mortality-driven outcomes as the primary measure of medical urgency and value (Callahan 2000; Gawande 2014). In health systems oriented toward preventing death, where infarcts, cancers, and organ failure command immediate attention, conditions like endometriosis, which rarely threaten lifespan but substantially impair wellbeing, are systematically deprioritized. This reflects a broader structural tendency within biomedicine to privilege “heroic” interventions (Gorovitz and MacIntyre 1976; Gawande 2014) over the management of chronic, non-fatal, and often gendered (Hamberg 2008; Hoffmann and Tarzian 2001) forms of suffering. As several scholars have noted, contemporary health policy and clinical research still equate significance with mortality risk, sidelining conditions that primarily undermine quality of life rather than survival (Nord 1999; Murray and Lopez 1996).

Endometriosis illustrates this enduring challenge. Affecting an estimated one in ten women of reproductive age, it involves the growth of endometrial-like tissue outside the uterus, leading to inflammation, scarring, and sometimes infertility (Giudice 2010; La Rosa et al. 2020). Despite its prevalence, diagnosis typically takes an average of seven to eight years (Ballard et al. 2006; De Corte et al. 2025). From an ethical perspective, this delay cannot be attributed to

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clinical complexity alone; it also reflects the ongoing difficulty of recognizing and validating women's experiences with pain within medical settings.

Diagnostic power as ethical responsibility

Historically, medical knowledge and practice have often been based on the adult male body and implicitly treated as the normative reference point (Hamberg 2008). Consequently, women's symptoms, hormonal cycles, and experiences of pain have sometimes been measured against frameworks that were never designed with them in mind (Pérez 2019). This structural bias has also been reinforced by the persistently low representation of women in gynecological leadership and academic decision-making positions, a historical irony that has shaped research priorities, training standards, and the very definition of what counts as clinically important (Hofler et al. 2016). Only in recent decades have women begun to enter senior roles in significant numbers, and the long delay in this shift has contributed, often unintentionally, to diagnostic gaps that affect women disproportionately (Acharya 2016).

Foucault argues that modern medicine derives its authority not only from its capacity to heal but also from its ability to see, classify, and name – what he calls “the medical gaze” (Foucault 1994). Yet historically, this gaze was overwhelmingly shaped by men, both in its epistemic foundations and institutional forms. The ability to define, categorize, and interpret illness was closely guarded within male-dominated medical professions, while the more human, relational dimensions of care were delegated to female nurses (Davies 1998; Patricia A. Donahue 1985; Reverby 1987; Witz 1992). Nursing, in turn, was systematically excluded from expert knowledge: a division reinforced through hierarchical training structures and even through linguistic barriers, such as the insistence on Latin terminology, which kept diagnostic authority firmly within the hands of physicians. These dynamics were not merely cultural but economic as well: exclusive access to specialized knowledge translated into professional power, higher status, and better remuneration. In this context, the medical gaze is not just a conceptual tool but a historically gendered one, and its moral responsibility is inseparable from the structures that shaped who was allowed to see, and who was expected merely to serve. As Fricker reminds us, when a person's account is undervalued because of who they are rather than what they say, epistemic injustice arises (Fricker 2009). In clinical contexts, this can occur when women's experiences of pain are filtered unconsciously through long-standing cultural assumptions about emotionality or sensitivity, rather than approached with open and empirical curiosity, when the medical gaze fails to truly see from women's perspectives.

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Commented [NB9]: very likely a male gaze, given who shaped the development of medicine. The human gaze was reserved for female nursing, with nurses (and societies more generally) being kept ignorant of "expert knowledge" - the insisting on Latin terms speaks to that. Economic consequences reinforce this pattern, as exclusive access to knowledge and skills is rewarded

At the moment, diagnosing endometriosis typically relies on invasive procedures, particularly laparoscopic surgery (Hsu et al. 2010), which can be debilitating for a few weeks, expensive and not universally accessible. Although non-surgical diagnostic approaches show promise (Nisenblat et al. 2016; Young 2024), an affordable and widely available test remains clinically out of reach for many patients, mainly due to medical unawareness. Transvaginal ultrasounds (TVU) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are a valid alternative to diagnostic laparoscopies. They demonstrated to have a high level of accuracy for ovarian endometriomas, deep endometriosis, pouch of Douglas obliteration and pelvic adhesions, when performed by experts (Guerriero et al. 2010; Leonardi et al. 2020; Roullier et al. 2021). As of 2020, less than 50% of OBGYNs in Canada, USA and UK and slightly more than 50% in Australia and New Zealand believed that TVUs could detect deep endometriosis in bowel and uterosacral ligament (Leonardi et al. 2020). The awareness and experience of OBGYNs and practitioners is therefore essential for a correct and quick diagnosis assumption, that could spare many patients costly and invasive diagnostic laparoscopies (Leonardi et al. 2020; Roullier et al. 2021). However, some cases are either still not visible by these techniques or the physicians' training still requires the patients to undergo a diagnostic laparoscopy, making the diagnosis long, costly, and difficult to access. This gap should not be considered only as a clinical challenge but also as an ethical one. This is mainly because the reliance on costly, specialized invasive procedures reinforces disparities in access to care, thus delaying recognition of a condition that already suffers from widespread underdiagnosis in at least one in ten women (Narasimhan et al. 2025). The consequences of such diagnostic hesitation reach far beyond mere inconvenience for delayed recognition of endometriosis can lead to persistent pain, impaired reproductive health, emotional distress, and substantial social and economic costs (De Graaff et al. 2013). These economic estimates, however, likely understate the true burden, as women's productivity losses are calculated primarily through paid labour. Given that women perform the majority of unpaid and informal care work (a form of labour typically excluded from cost-of-illness models) (WGEKN et al. 2007; ILO 2018; UN WOMEN 2019) the economic impact of endometriosis is structurally underestimated.

Existing studies also show that the financial costs of endometriosis are significant. For example, direct medical expenses including but not limited to hospitalizations, medications, and outpatient care have been estimated to be approximately in the range of US \$1,100 in Canada and over US \$12,000 in the United States, per patient annually (Soliman et al. 2016). When increased absenteeism as well as reduced productivity and work performance are included in the calculation as the elements of indirect costs, the economic

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impact extends far beyond individual patients, revealing a systemic gap in how societies recognize and respond to women's health needs (Narasimhan et al. 2025). Comprehensive healthcare strategies that emphasize timely diagnosis, workplace and social support are indispensable in mitigating the burden of endometriosis in women.

The true impact of menstrual health conditions, particularly endometriosis, on women seems to be underestimated (Narasimhan et al. 2025), and this long existing pattern of underestimation is not only a clinical issue, but also a reflection of a broader (and seemingly centuries old) ethical concern. It brings us once again to the persistent undervaluing of women's health and the economic invisibility of conditions that primarily affect women.

From invisibility to integrity: ethical priorities for reform

Ethically speaking, the principle of non-maleficence encompasses more than just avoiding direct harm. It includes the duty to prevent avoidable suffering as well. When long delays in diagnosis persist, they highlight a system that still struggles to hear and acknowledge certain kinds of pain. Phrases such as "it's normal, just endure it", frequently heard by women when they report menstrual or pelvic pain in clinical settings. Though they seem benign, they subtly undermine the legitimacy of the women's experience and contribute to diagnostic delay in female conditions. In these moments, the diagnostic encounter risks losing its therapeutic purpose. In order to restore trust and achieve fairness in medicine, the clinical space must become a place where uncertainty invites further inquiry rather than straight dismissal, and where listening is understood as an integral part of clinical care. Gender-sensitive medicine offers one such path forward that extends beyond tokenistic inclusion alone or awareness campaigns, encompassing significant and meaningful change through rebuilding diagnostic and therapeutic standards on more inclusive and representative clinical practice.

There are at least three areas where meaningful progress can be made:

Education and clinical training

Medical education can play a pivotal role in reducing gender bias in the clinic and improving the recognition of women's health concerns. Incorporating modules on gender differences in disease presentation, as well as courses that encourage meaningful communication, prioritizing active listening with the patients can help clinicians approach symptoms, such as chronic pelvic pain, with greater empathy and awareness. For instance, empirical evidence shows that women tend to wait longer for pain relief in emergency settings and that their pain is more frequently attributed to psychological causes (Hoffmann and

Tarzian 2001). Addressing such findings through education can promote reflection rather than blame.

Diagnostic pathways and accountability

General practitioners and OBGYNs should be updated on the current advancements of cheap, non-invasive diagnostic tools such as TVUs and MRI and how to correctly interpret them, or rather recognize that patients should be redirected to a more specialized center, instead of contributing to diagnostic delay, dismissal of symptoms, or to diagnostic inequality due to the high costs. Improving the structure of care is equally significant. Implementing clear referral pathways for cases of suspected endometriosis could shorten the lengthy diagnostic periods many patients experience, often spending years of moving between general practitioners and specialists (Davenport et al. 2023; Cromeens et al. 2021; The Lancet Regional Health – Western Pacific 2025; Kok et al. 2024). Monitoring diagnostic timeline data and access to expert centers would make it easier to identify where delays occur and how they can be reduced. In this sense, accountability needs not to be punitive, rather it should be a tool for institutional learning and improvement across health systems.

Research equity

Research priorities in biomedicine often reflect broader sociocultural patterns. Although endometriosis affects approximately 10% of (or one in ten) women of reproductive age worldwide (as many as 190 million individuals) (WHO 2025; Parasar et al. 2017), research on endometriosis remains relatively underfunded compared to conditions that primarily affect men (Ellis et al. 2022; Viganò et al. 2024). For instance, while erectile dysfunction, affecting approximately 8 – 10% of men under 40, has generated over 16,000 indexed publications in the last 50 years. In contrast, dyspareunia, a frequent symptom of endometriosis involving pain during intercourse in women, has generated only around 6,500 publications¹. Gendered assumptions can have a serious impact on what is considered as medical priority and what as secondary, especially in a research culture where funding is highly competitive. Redirecting research attention to endometriosis especially toward the goal of inventing non-invasive diagnostic methods, treatments with fewer side effects, and improving quality-of-life outcomes would better align medical inquiry with the diversity of patient needs.

¹ The query: "dyspareunia"[MeSH Terms] OR "dyspareunia"[All Fields] yields 6583 results. The query: "erectile dysfunction"[MeSH Terms] OR ("erectile"[All Fields] AND "dysfunction"[All Fields]) OR "erectile dysfunction"[All Fields] yields 31449 results. Both queries were executed on the 31st of October 2025.

In each of these domains, namely education, diagnosis, and research, the goal is not to assign blame, but to build systems that listen more carefully, represent more accurately, and respond more fairly to all who seek care.

Beyond fertility: restoring autonomy

Historically, marriage and childbirth were often prescribed as remedies for women's unexplained illnesses, including what was once labeled "hysteria" (Showalter 1997; Tasca et al. 2012; King 2016). Despite the advances in medicine, traces of this mindset occasionally persist. For instance, women with endometriosis are sometimes told that becoming pregnant might relieve their symptoms because menstrual cycles are temporarily suspended during gestation and due to the effect of progesterone on lowering estrogens, although pregnancy may not always be a feasible option for many (Leeners et al. 2018; Wisbey 2023). Although this suggestion may be offered in good faith, it still reflects an enduring tendency to view women's health primarily through the lens of reproduction. Such framing, even when it is unintentional, can narrow the focus of care and overlook the diversity of women's needs, life goals, and circumstances.

While the symptoms of endometriosis are clearly connected to the female reproductive system, its manifestations and treatment implications reach far beyond reproduction. As Jones argues, understanding endometriosis requires moving past the old metaphor of the "wandering womb" and acknowledging the complex interplay between biological processes, sociological framings and cultural narratives (Jones 2015). Only by recognizing how bodily systems and social expectations intersect, patients, clinicians, and researchers can begin to address the deeper systematic challenges that endometriosis presents.

Therefore, a genuinely person-centered ethically informed approach to endometriosis shifts attention from reproduction to reproductive autonomy, the freedom to decide whether, when, and how to pursue pregnancy, and grounds care in the patient's broader well-being. This means that treatment should not only consider fertility outcomes but also address pain management, participation in work and social life, sexual health, and overall quality of life.

As broadly emphasized in literature on autonomy, it should not be understood as an isolated act of choice, but rather as one that emerges within social, economic, and institutional contexts (Sherwin 1992; Verkerk 2001; Mackenzie and Stoljar 2000; Childress 2022). Supporting women's autonomy, therefore, necessitates more than respecting personal decisions; it demands creating conditions in which those decisions can be made freely and meaningfully. Promoting gender justice in reproductive medicine means both recognizing women as moral agents and ensuring that surrounding systems enable them,

rather than constrain, their capacity to act as such. Thus, acknowledging endometriosis as a chronic condition within local and international health frameworks would be a significant step toward achieving gender justice and equity in sexual health medicine. Such recognition could facilitate public or insurance-based coverage for surgical and non-surgical interventions, enable formal eligibility for disability benefits in advanced cases, and help normalize workplace accommodations for endometriosis patients, such as flexible scheduling or remote work, during severe flare-ups of the symptoms. Ensuring that women across diverse settings can access timely diagnosis, effective treatment, and supportive working conditions is not merely a matter of convenience; it is a matter of justice.

The ethics of attention in gender medicine

The ethical dimensions of endometriosis extend beyond the gynecology clinics. They affect families, workplaces, health systems, and touch the broader social fabric (De Graaff et al. 2013). When the pain of so many continues to be under-recognized, the effects are shared: emotional, economic, and moral. Each delay in diagnosis represents time lost; each missed opportunity for understanding diminishes collective trust in healthcare.

Recognizing endometriosis as a distinct medical condition was an important first step, it transformed a condition from something that was once viewed through moral or psychological lenses into a legitimate area of clinical concern. Yet ethical practice requires ongoing attentiveness: ensuring that endometriosis remains visible in policy discussions, medical curricula, research agendas, and, most importantly, in the everyday encounters between patients and clinicians.

Not having one's pain recognized is an experience many women describe not only in clinical encounters but also in everyday life, often leading to feelings of isolation, uncertainty, and self-doubt. In this context, online peer-support communities—such as the large and active endometriosis forums on Reddit—have become crucial spaces where patients can narrate their experiences without fear of dismissal. These platforms provide testimonial validation, shared hermeneutical resources, and collective knowledge that many women struggle to access within formal healthcare settings. The anonymity and accessibility of these communities lower the threshold for disclosure, sustain mutual recognition, and often empower women to seek second opinions or advocate for diagnostic procedures when their symptoms have been repeatedly minimized. Their emergence as parallel systems of affirmation highlights, by contrast, the ongoing inadequacy of clinical environments in offering the attentive listening and epistemic credibility that patients require

(ESSI 2025; Ziebland and Wyke 2012; Coulson et al. 2016). Far from being marginal or anecdotal, these peer networks reveal how persistent gaps in medical attention are increasingly being filled by patient-driven spaces of meaning-making and support (Sinha and Serin 2024).

As Simone Weil vividly observed, attention is the purest form of generosity (Weil 1952). In medical ethics, attention is the act that restores the patient's humanity, transforming them from an object of study into a partner in care, recognizing their vulnerability. Gender-sensitive medicine, in this sense, is not only a matter of reforming procedures, it also reflects a deeper moral orientation: the willingness to listen with care when women speak of their pain.

Conclusion

Seeing, naming, and acting remain the essential ethical movements of justice in medicine. The history of hysteria shows that when women's pain is misnamed, it is easily misunderstood; the contemporary story of endometriosis reveals how unheard pain can become embedded in clinical routines, producing delay not by accident alone but through longstanding epistemic habits of disbelief.

The challenge ahead is therefore twofold.

On the pragmatic side, closing the diagnostic gap requires better training, clearer referral pathways, and equitable access to accurate non-invasive diagnostic tools. Medical curricula must integrate gender-sensitive teaching; practitioners need up-to-date competencies in recognizing endometriosis and other chronic pain conditions; and health systems must reduce the financial and geographical barriers that prevent timely access to expert care. Research priorities should shift toward developing affordable diagnostic methods and improving quality-of-life outcomes, so that structural disbelief cannot continue to translate into structural delay.

On the ethical side, clinical practice must renew its commitment to attention as a moral act. Listening, believing, and taking women's testimony seriously are not optional gestures of empathy but essential elements of diagnostic reasoning. Epistemic justice must become a standard of care: a recognition that credibility is not simply earned by patients, but also granted – or withheld – by clinicians and the systems that train them.

Endometriosis thus offers more than a clinical puzzle; it exposes a deeper misalignment between what medicine prioritizes and what many women need. Only when biological precision and ethical attention advance together can medicine genuinely move beyond its "hysterical" past and toward a practice that recognizes pain not by who speaks it, but by the seriousness of its impact.

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